

Fugaku UWLCM scaling

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1 Introduction

Scaling tests of UWLCM model on the RIKEN Fugaku cluster. Using the UWLCM Spack environment (gcc@12, Fujitsu-MPI). Work is part of the Hanami project. UWLCM domain decomposition works in one horizontal direction for MPI and in the other for OpenMP. Fugaku nodes have 48 CPU cores. 1 MPI process per node was used. Tests were done with the moist thermal setup. Similar tests on Cyfronet Prometheus are described in: GMD paper. Run scripts can be found at: UWLCM-recipes

2 Bulk 1-moment 1D grid scaling

Weak scaling with domain extending in one direction (the one along which MPI domain decomposition is done). $n_x = 96 \times N_{nodes}$, $n_y = n_z = 96$, $X = 3600 \times N_{nodes}$.

3 Bulk 1-moment 2D grid scaling

Weak scaling with domain extending in both horizontal directions . $n_x = n_y = 96 \times \sqrt{N_{nodes}}$, $n_z = 96$, $X = Y = 3600 \times \sqrt{N_{nodes}}$.

4 Lagrangian strong scaling

$n_x = n_y = 480$, $n_z = 96$, $X = Y = 18000$, $N_{SD} = 100$.

5 Conclusions

Lagrangian microphysics are 1 to 2 orders of magnitude slower than bulk microphysics. This is mitigated by using GPUs to model super-droplets on other clusters. Throwing multiple CPU nodes to handle the SD workload doesn't help - strong scaling is not effective (why?). However, weak scaling performance is acceptable. Could be improved by MPI domain decomposition in two dimensions (compare 1D grid scaling with 2D grid scaling). Results suggest that large CPU clusters are good for large number of Eulerian grid points with simple microphysics (bulk), but GPU accelerated clusters are much better for the super-droplet microphysics.